

The Trauma THOMPSON Challenge 2025: Structured description of the challenge design

CHALLENGE ORGANIZATION

Title

Use the title to convey the essential information on the challenge mission.

The Trauma THOMPSON Challenge 2025

Challenge acronym

Preferable, provide a short acronym of the challenge (if any).

T3 Challenge 2025

Challenge abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

The Trauma THOMPSON Challenge 2025 aims to inspire participants to develop advanced algorithms for autonomous remote instruction systems capable of providing real-time guidance and support to medical professionals for humanitarian aid in austere and disconnected settings, such as disaster response. Such system will be able to recognize current action, predict next action, track hands, highlight medical tools and answer medical questions to assist inexperienced critical care providers with essential medical instructions and information. It will improve care quality and reduce human errors under the high-stake scenarios where lives are in grave danger. Leveraging a unique dataset of egocentric videos capturing unscripted lifesaving medical procedures, participants will be tasked with developing algorithms for a range of challenging tasks, including action recognition, action anticipation, hand tracking, tool detection, realism assessment, and Visual Question Answering (VQA). The dataset encompasses diverse lifesaving procedures performed under various settings, especially just-in-time procedures with makeshift tools, where conventional medical tools are unavailable and emergency procedure has to be performed to save lives with daily items. Baseline methods are provided to facilitate participant engagement, with the ultimate goal of fostering innovations that can advance critical care technology and improve procedure outcomes for patients. The challenge is underlain by recognizing activities, patterns of motion, objects, and similarity of procedures, as well as discovering hidden states of unscripted emergency care procedures. Through this competition, we aim to catalyze the development of innovative artificial intelligence solutions that can significantly enhance medical assistance in remote and resource-constrained environments for humanitarian medicine.

Challenge keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the challenge.

Deep learning, Action recognition, Action anticipation, Just-in-time procedures, Hand tracking, Object detection, Realism assessment, Visual question answering

Year

2025

Novelty of the challenge

Briefly describe the novelty of the challenge.

The Trauma THOMPSON Challenge introduces a medical procedure dataset aimed at driving development of autonomous instruction systems for emergency care under low resource environments [1]. This system will have the capability to recognize current actions, anticipate next actions, track hand movements, detect and highlight medical tools, and respond to medical queries. It can support inexperienced critical care providers with crucial medical guidance and information. By enhancing the quality of care and minimizing human errors, the system aims to improve outcomes in high-stakes situations where lives are at significant risk. To the best of our knowledge, our dataset, comprising professionally annotated video clips, high quality bounding boxes of hands and medical tools, realism scores, and per frame VQA annotations, stands out as the first unscripted egocentric medical procedure dataset, with expansive scale and diverse settings. They are recorded and collected by medical experts performing emergency care procedures on different very realistic medical simulators. We also collected videos of just-in-time critical care procedures performed with makeshift tools. Such procedures are very important to save lives when traditional medical tools and instruments are not available while lives are under high stake. The support systems with such capabilities are not developed yet. Each video is annotated with ground-truth actions, in the form of verb-noun combinations, and timestamps indicating the duration of each action. The verb noun combinations help provide improved medical explainability to model predictions, with the verb describing the action and the noun describing the target of the action. Additionally, each video is further annotated with hand tracking, object detection, and a realism score, which can provide essential medical information during procedures. Notably, the actions depicted and performed in the videos are unscripted, reflecting real-world scenarios encountered in humanitarian medicine, especially in disconnected settings. Furthermore, each clip is assigned a specific life-saving skill relevant to humanitarian medicine, ensuring the dataset's applicability to critical scenarios. Thus, the Trauma THOMPSON dataset represents a valuable contribution to the field, offering researchers a great resource to propel advancements in autonomous medical guidance and ultimately improve patient procedure outcomes in challenging environments.

Task description and application scenarios

Briefly describe the application scenarios for the tasks in the challenge.

This year will be the second Trauma THOMPSON Challenge. The first Trauma THOMPSON Challenge was held as a satellite event of the 26th International Conference on Medical Image Computing and Computer Assisted Intervention, MICCAI 2023. The second challenge will be different from the first challenge, with new data and new tasks that are more challenging. The first Trauma THOMPSON Challenge contained 2 tracks and 4 tasks in total. Track 1 included action recognition, action anticipation, and procedure recognition. Track 2 was the VQA challenge. For the action recognition task, the objective was to classify the actions performed during a medical procedure, given an egocentric view video and the accompanying timestamp information. For the action anticipation task, the objective was to predict the next actions in a medical procedure, given an egocentric view video alongside timestamp information. For procedure recognition, the objective was to classify the medical procedure type. For the VQA task, the objective was to assess the accuracy of AI models in understanding both visual information and textual queries about the lifesaving interventional (LSI) procedures. The questions asked about direct information that could be seen from the image, such as "Is there bleeding?" or "What limb is

injured?". The dataset contained hundreds of annotated videos representing 5 unscripted procedures vital for LSI procedures. The procedures included cricothyroidotomy, intraosseous infusion, needle thoracostomy, tourniquet application, and tube thoracostomy.

For the second Trauma THOMPSON Challenge, there will also be 5 tasks in total. Task 1 is action recognition and anticipation of medical procedures, including regular procedures and just-in-time procedures. Task 2 and task 3 are emergency procedure hand tracking and tool detection respectively. Task 4 is realism detection. Task 5 is VQA with more questions and answers. Action recognition and anticipation are crucial because understanding both the current and anticipated actions of a mentor helps guide the mentee's tasks. Visual Question Answering (VQA) plays a vital role in enabling inexperienced caregivers to engage in a dialogue with the AI mentor, allowing them to ask questions during critical, life-saving interventions. Realism is important for accurate tracking and a more immersive, effective learning experience. Hand tracking helps evaluate the mentee's proficiency by monitoring their hand movements, which is essential for skill development. Tool detection aids in ensuring the correct tools are identified and used, particularly in high-stakes environments. These tasks were specifically chosen because they are directly applicable and highly relevant in a tele-mentoring system, where real-time feedback and guidance are very important.

Action recognition presents an important aspect of surgical assistance, as it allows doctors to act quickly, which is vital in austere circumstances and settings. Action anticipation involves algorithms being able to forecast future steps with limited to no knowledge of previous procedures or the patient's condition. The challenge of this year's task is using one model to simultaneously recognize and predict actions. It simulates situations where healthcare providers must act quickly and efficiently to perform essential lifesaving procedures on patients. Additionally, the just-in-time procedures are more challenging than regular procedures for algorithms to learn patterns because of the unconventional tools, unscripted nature, and higher variability of the actions. The procedures involve makeshift tools, which makes the tasks harder and more applicable to real life scenarios where medical tools are not available. However, feedback from algorithms on these procedures must still be accurate to maintain high quality assistance in remote environments where equipment may not be readily available. Realism detection involves assessing the degree of realism exhibited by simulated patients and injuries. This new task can be applied in various aspects of model training to train algorithms on the most realistic procedures to improve accuracy in a real field environment. The new VQA challenge focuses on answering questions that cannot be directly inferred from the scene, such as "Is the patient choking?". Finally, the new hand tracking tasks in this challenge help support decision-making in surgical environments but also includes many challenges for algorithms to perform well, including the overlapping of hands. Therefore, although some tasks for the competition this year come from the last challenge, the tasks this year are much more challenging and relevant to real life scenarios due to inclusion of new data and tasks that are imperative in real life applications.

FURTHER INFORMATION FOR CONFERENCE ORGANIZERS

Workshop

If the challenge is part of a workshop, please indicate the workshop.

N/A

Duration

How long does the challenge take?

2 Hours

In case you selected half or full day, please explain why you need a long slot for your challenge.

N/A

Expected number of participants

Please explain the basis of your estimate (e.g. numbers from previous challenges) and/or provide a list of potential participants and indicate if they have already confirmed their willingness to contribute.

We estimate that there will be around 200 participants. Our last challenge included over 70 participants, but we expect this number to increase significantly because of the increased number of tasks and uniqueness of our data. Because of the diverse nature of our challenge with 8 different tasks and the availability of baseline algorithms, we believe our challenge will attract numerous participants focused on different applications of machine learning, and it will pose an interesting challenge to many for participants to develop algorithms which can best learn the data.

Publication and future plans

Please indicate if you plan to coordinate a publication of the challenge results.

Yes, we plan to have a proceeding.

Space and hardware requirements

Organizers of on-site challenges must provide a fair computing environment for all participants. For instance, algorithms should run on the same computing platform provided to all.

projectors, computers, monitors, loud speakers, microphones

TASK 1: Action recognition and anticipation of regular and just in-time procedures

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

The task of action recognition and anticipation in medical procedures challenges participants to simultaneously recognize current actions and predict next actions on egocentric medical procedure videos. This dual-task formulation closely mirrors real-world scenarios and needs in emergency medicine, battlefield medicine, and disaster response, where accurate and timely interpretation of medical actions is crucial for effective intervention. A key challenge in this task is the diverse and uncontrolled nature of medical environments, where procedures are often unscripted and highly variable. Numerous action classification benchmarks exist in the field, such as UCF101, HMDB51, Kinetics, Something-Something, and AVA. However, the Trauma THOMPSON dataset stands out as the first egocentric video dataset specifically designed for medical procedure action recognition and anticipation, bringing unique value to the field.

This challenge extends beyond conventional procedural settings by incorporating just-in-time procedures, which involve the use of improvised tools, such as belts, screwdrivers, and clothing, to perform life-saving interventions in austere and resource-limited conditions. Recognizing and anticipating these actions is particularly difficult, as they deviate from standard medical protocols and demand adaptability to unpredictable scenarios. Participants must develop algorithms capable of classifying current actions while forecasting future steps using only observed visual cues, with minimal prior knowledge of the full procedure being performed. Success in this task will advance AI-driven support for medical responders, enabling proactive decision-making and improving trauma care delivery in critical, time-sensitive situations.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

Low resource environment, Action recognition, Action anticipation, Makeshift tools

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

Yupeng Zhuo, Juan Wachs, Eddie Zhang, Andrew W. Kirkpatrick, Jessica Mckee, Edgar Rojas-Muñoz, Brian Vanvoorst, Jin Tae Kwak, Stas Tiomkin

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

Yupeng Zhuo, Juan Wachs

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

MICCAI

b) Report the platform (e.g. grand-challenge.org) used to run the challenge.

grand-challenge.org

c) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

<https://thompson-challenge.grand-challenge.org> This is the grand-challenge website.

<https://coolstudy.ca/miccai-challenge/> This is the website to download the dataset.

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed (e.g. only (semi-) automatic methods allowed).

Fully automatic

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or to publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets.

No additional data allowed

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

May participate but not eligible for awards and not listed in leaderboard

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

1st place: \$300

2nd place: \$150

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly. Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

Submission of a paper (min 6 pages, max 12 pages) is not required for participating in the challenge and appearing on the leaderboard, but it is required for eligibility of awards.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

Algorithms will be assessed automatically online. To submit results, the participants need to containerize their codes with Docker and upload them to the Trauma THOMPSON grand-challenge website, as described by the submission instructions of the grand-challenge website (<https://grand-challenge.org/documentation/prepare-your-code-for-containerization/>). The submitted containers will be automatically evaluated, and the results and rankings will be visible on the grand-challenge website after a few minutes. Participants can request withdrawals at any time. Sample Docker container codes for all tasks will be provided by the organizing team.

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

Participants of all tasks are permitted to make multiple submissions, with only the last run being officially considered as the final result. However, all participants are restricted to a maximum of 10 submissions per task over the entire challenge period, excluding failed attempts due to incorrect formatting. The restrictions on the number of allowed submissions will prevent leaderboard engineering, ensuring a fair evaluation by discouraging excessive trial-and-error tuning and promoting generalizable model performance. The same submission policy is applied to both individual and group participants.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
- the registration date/period
- the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
- the submission date(s)

- associated workshop days (if any)
- the release date(s) of the results

Challenge website: Apr. 1st, 2025

Participants will be able to register for the challenge on the grand-challenge website.

Train and test data release: Apr. 15th, 2025

Both train and test data will be released.

Containerized algorithm submission deadline: Aug. 15th, 2025

All participants must submit their containerized algorithms by this date to participate in the challenge and appear on the leaderboard.

Summary report submission: Sep. 1st, 2025

All participants must submit their report papers by this date to be eligible for awards.

Invitation to participate: Sep. 1st, 2025

Winners of the challenge (with both contain and paper submission) will be invited to present at the conference. The presentation types will be determined by the availability of the participants.

Winner announcement: Sept. 23-27, 2025 (Challenge at MICCAI)

Top 3 performing teams and winners will be announced during the satellite event at the MICCAI conference.

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

Ethics approval is not necessary for the data.

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

The organizing team will provide sample Docker containers to help all participants to package their codes for automatic evaluations on the grand-challenge website, allowing the participants to adhere to the specified input and output formats. The organizing team will use grand-challenge API and the rankings will be automatically produced. The instructions and details are available on the grand-challenge website documentation (<https://grand-challenge.org/documentation/automated-evaluation/>). Additionally, the organizing team will provide codes of some baseline models for each task and the codes for evaluation. Since the challenge has not started, the codes for proposal review can be accessed through this link (<https://github.com/zhuoyp/TraumaTHOMPSON/blob/main/README.md>).

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

The code from participating teams will remain private. However, the methodologies of the top 3 algorithms will be shared upon announcing the winners. Participants are also free to publish their methodologies once the dataset is made publicly available.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

The organizers will not participate in the challenge, so no participants will have access to the dataset beforehand to ensure fairness.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

Decision support, Assistance

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Classification, Prediction

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

The final biomedical application is for physicians and untrained personnel to perform diagnoses or life-saving resuscitative procedures in resource-limited environments.

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

The challenge dataset is acquired from military medics and medical experts as they perform specific procedures on various medical simulators.

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

All images are extracted from egocentric videos recorded using head-mounted cameras, such as the GoPro 7.

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

The dataset encompasses videos with camera information and annotations with corresponding timestamps.

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

Manikins are used, and no human subjects are involved.

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

- Interosseous insertion: shoulder, limb
- Needle thoracostomy: chest
- Tourniquet application: limb
- Tracheostomy: larynx
- Tube thoracostomy: chest

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

The algorithm target is the simulated wound area on manikins.

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Accuracy

DATA SETS

Data source(s)

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

The procedure videos are captured from egocentric view with by head-mounting the camera, GoPro 7 (minimum). The device is capable of capturing videos in MP4 format with high frame rates and resolution, ensuring accurate visual representation of the medical procedures. We have collected various procedures under different environments to increase the diversity of our dataset.

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

The medical professionals followed the video collection guidelines adapted from the EPIC Kitchen challenge [2]. The cameras were head mounted to obtain egocentric views of medical procedures. The videos were recorded in controlled environments simulating field conditions, focusing on procedures performed by military medics and medical experts. Each video captured the use of medical tools in real-time scenarios. Protocols for imaging included optimal lighting setups, ensuring minimal shadows and clear visibility of tools, and maintaining consistent camera angles to standardize dataset quality. The obtained videos were stored as MP4 files. They were annotated by timestamps and also extracted into frames. Both the annotated videos and frames are provided for the challenge.

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

The procedure videos were collected by trained military medics and medical professionals with extensive experience in performing the documented procedures, including the representatives from Purdue University, The Geneva Foundation, Madigan Army Medical center, the Ready Medic One Research Team, and the University of Calgary.

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

All of the physicians have over 10 years of clinical experience. They mounted the GoPro camera on their heads and adjusted the camera angle for the video collection. Ideally, the hands were in the center of the image during the procedure.

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

The train and test cases contain video clips of procedures performed by military medics and medical experts. One training case includes the full annotations of the current action, the next action, the starting timestamp, the end timestamp, and the corresponding video clip. An action is defined as a verb and noun pair. One testing case is one video clip.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

The dataset consists of a total of 3,717 cases, with 2,930 cases (80%) for training and 787 cases (20%) for testing.

c) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

The total number of cases is based on availability of videos. The dataset is split based on a common practice in machine learning research, 80% for training and 20% for testing. The training set can be further split into training and validation set based on the needs of the participants.

d) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

Although this classification dataset is imbalanced, the class distribution is chosen according to the real-world distribution. There are 42 verb classes, 42 noun classes, and 124 action classes for the regular procedures, and 28 verb classes, 32 noun classes, and 89 action classes for the just-in-time procedures.

e) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

The regular procedure data is published and the just-in-time procedure data is unpublished.

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

The dataset annotations include the start and end timestamps, along with the corresponding current and next action for each video clip. The expected test output is action, verb, and noun labels. After recording, physicians will annotate their own procedural videos by providing timestamps, action labels, and question-answer pairs related to the procedure steps in the collected footage. 5 human annotators were involved in creating and reviewing the annotations.

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

We provided some guidelines to the physicians for the annotations as follows. Firstly, the annotation should be in the present tense. For example, remove, and position. Secondly, the annotation should be in verb-noun pairs. For example, incise skin, and take needles. Thirdly, there is no need to have pronouns in the annotations. For example, the physicians don't need to state who is doing the incision or cut. Fourthly, do not reveal any identities in the annotation for the privacy protection of the physicians. Fifthly, if an action spans a long-time duration, the physicians can annotate the video clip multiple times with the same action label and different timestamps. For example, if the action "Palpate landmark" lasts over 5 seconds in a video, then it should be annotated twice with the same action label and different timestamps.

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

All of the physicians have over 10 years of experience in the clinical settings.

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

We have the specific annotation for each video clip and don't need to deal with multiple annotations for one case.

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

After collecting the procedure videos and annotations from the physicians, preprocessing was performed. For the raw videos, we extracted frame for all videos. Then, we parsed the annotations into the verb and noun pairs and clustered the classes for similar verbs and nouns. For example, "pick" and "take" are clustered into the same verb class.

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter-and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

One possible error source is the starting timestamp and the ending timestamp for the actions. However, as stated above, our annotations are provided by military medics and medical experts and are peer-reviewed to minimize potential errors on the timestamps. In this way, the timing error should be less than a second and can be neglected.

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

N/A

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

We use a class-agnostic approach to evaluate the action accuracy, allowing for a broader assessment of performance independent of specific category distributions. An action is a verb and noun pair. For example, in "take scalpel", "take" is a verb, "scalpel" is a noun and "take scalpel" is an action. For each action, we sample a sequence of 32 frames in the beginning of the action clip [3]. To compute the accuracy, we count the number of correctly predicted current actions and the number of correctly predicted next actions. Then, divide it by the total number of current actions and next actions in the test set. The performance will be computed as $(\text{correct_current_action} + \text{correct_next_action}) / (\text{total_current_action} + \text{total_next_action})$. We will evaluate the top 1 accuracy of the verbs, nouns, and actions.

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

We choose accuracy as our evaluation metric because it is a very popular and common method for classification tasks.

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking.

Since action recognition and action anticipation are performed simultaneously, we will use the total top 1 accuracy of all actions (current action+next action) for ranking. Therefore, a model performing well in action recognition but poorly in action anticipation may not win the challenge. We will show the accuracy for regular procedures, just-in-time procedures, and both procedures combined, but use the accuracy on both procedures combined as the basis for ranking. If the action accuracies for different teams are the same, we will use the total top 1 accuracy of the verbs for tie breaking. If the verb accuracies are the same, we use the total top 1 accuracy of the nouns. Higher accuracy indicates better model performance on this task.

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

If the algorithm submitted by participants misses an action or an answer, it will be treated as an incorrect result and receive an accuracy of 0 in task evaluation. Therefore, missing results will negatively impact model performance, so we do not recommend that algorithms produce incomplete test results.

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

Since the task is a classification task, we will use accuracy to rank performance. We want the submitted algorithms to perform well in both action recognition and action anticipation simultaneously, as the model will be more useful in real world applications, so the algorithms need to have good and balanced performances in both categories. The successful classification of actions is more important than just verbs and nouns, so we use action accuracies for ranking.

Statistical analyses

a) Provide details for the statistical methods used in the scope of the challenge analysis. This may include

- description of the missing data handling,
- details about the assessment of variability of rankings,
- description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions, required for the particular statistical approach, or
- indication of any software product that was used for all data analysis methods.

Due to poor visualization of some actions, the corresponding annotations cannot be correctly generated and thus are deleted from the dataset. The cleaned-up annotations are distributed to the participants.

b) Justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used.

This is the most common method of dealing with missing data [4].

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

We intend to evaluate the performance of the algorithms using ensemble methods, including a linear combination, majority voting, and consensus, to determine whether these techniques could identify a potential winner. However, this analysis will be conducted solely for informational purposes and may serve as a baseline for future iterations of the challenge.

TASK 2: Emergency procedure hand tracking

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Hand tracking is a challenging but significant task. Such algorithm can assist care providers to identify proper tools in a more straightforward manner. The task involves precisely capturing hand movements, classifying hand types (left or right hand), and recognizing medical tools in real-time. The ability to perform these tasks effectively is integral to enhancing decision-making in critical situations, and the presence of gloves makes these tasks even harder. The challenge focuses on advancing algorithms that can achieve high levels of accuracy and precision in detecting and tracking hands, even under the unpredictable conditions often encountered in medical environments. The decent performance of the task will largely improve the efficiency and quality of the surgeries. Added to it, it ensures the safety of patients, especially in urgent emergencies when patients meet the threaten of death.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

Emergency procedure, Hand tracking

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

Yupeng Zhuo, Juan Wachs, Xiyue Chen, Andrew W. Kirkpatrick, Jessica Mckee, Edgar Rojas-Muñoz, Brian Vanvoorst, Jin Tae Kwak, Stas Tiomkin

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

Yupeng Zhuo, Juan Wachs

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

MICCAI

b) Report the platform (e.g. grand-challenge.org) used to run the challenge.

grand-challenge.org

c) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

<https://thompson-challenge.grand-challenge.org> This is the grand-challenge website.

<https://coolstudy.ca/miccai-challenge/> This is the website to download the dataset.

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed (e.g. only (semi-) automatic methods allowed).

Fully automatic

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or to publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets.

No additional data allowed

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

May participate but not eligible for awards and not listed in leaderboard

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

1st place: \$300

2nd place: \$150

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly. Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

Submission of a paper (min 6 pages, max 12 pages) is not required for participating in the challenge and appearing on the leaderboard, but it is required for eligibility of awards.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

Algorithms will be assessed automatically online. To submit results, the participants need to containerize their codes with Docker and upload them to the Trauma THOMPSON grand-challenge website, as described by the submission instructions of the grand-challenge website (<https://grand-challenge.org/documentation/prepare-your-code-for-containerization/>). The submitted containers will be automatically evaluated, and the results and rankings will be visible on the grand-challenge website after a few minutes. Participants can request withdrawals at any time. Sample Docker container codes for all tasks will be provided by the organizing team.

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

Participants of all tasks are permitted to make multiple submissions, with only the last run being officially considered as the final result. However, all participants are restricted to a maximum of 10 submissions per task over the entire challenge period, excluding failed attempts due to incorrect formatting. The restrictions on the number of allowed submissions will prevent leaderboard engineering, ensuring a fair evaluation by discouraging excessive trial-and-error tuning and promoting generalizable model performance. The same submission policy is applied to both individual and group participants.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
- the registration date/period
- the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
- the submission date(s)
- associated workshop days (if any)
- the release date(s) of the results

Challenge website: Apr. 1st, 2025

Participants will be able to register for the challenge on the grand-challenge website.

Train and test data release: Apr. 15th, 2025

Both train and test data will be released.

Containerized algorithm submission deadline: Aug. 15th, 2025

All participants must submit their containerized algorithms by this date to participate in the challenge and appear

on the leaderboard.

Summary report submission: Sep. 1st, 2025

All participants must submit their report papers by this date to be eligible for awards.

Invitation to participate: Sep. 1st, 2025

Winners of the challenge (with both contain and paper submission) will be invited to present at the conference.

The presentation types will be determined by the availability of the participants.

Winner announcement: Sept. 23-27, 2025 (Challenge at MICCAI)

Top 3 performing teams and winners will be announced during the satellite event at the MICCAI conference.

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

Ethics approval is not necessary for the data.

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

The organizing team will provide sample Docker containers to help all participants to package their codes for automatic evaluations on the grand-challenge website, allowing the participants to adhere to the specified input and output formats. The organizing team will use grand-challenge API and the rankings will be automatically produced. The instructions and details are available on the grand-challenge website documentation (<https://grand-challenge.org/documentation/automated-evaluation/>). Additionally, the organizing team will provide codes of some baseline models for each task and the codes for evaluation. Since the challenge has not started, the codes for proposal review can be accessed through this link

(<https://github.com/zhuoyp/TraumaTHOMPSON/blob/main/README.md>).

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

The code from participating teams will remain private. However, the methodologies of the top 3 algorithms will be shared upon announcing the winners. Participants are also free to publish their methodologies once the dataset is made publicly available.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

The organizers will not participate in the challenge, so no participants will have access to the dataset beforehand to ensure fairness.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

Decision support, Assistance

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization

- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Detection,Localization,Tracking

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

The final biomedical application is for physicians and untrained personnel to perform diagnoses or life-saving resuscitative procedures in resource-limited environments.

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

The challenge dataset is acquired from military medics and medical experts as they perform specific procedures on various medical simulators.

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

All images are extracted from egocentric videos recorded using head-mounted cameras, such as the GoPro 7.

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

The dataset encompasses annotation files in COCO format, extracted frames, and videos.

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

Manikins are used, and no human subjects are involved.

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary,

differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

- Interosseous insertion: shoulder, limb
- Needle thoracostomy: chest
- Tourniquet application: limb
- Tracheostomy: larynx
- Tube thoracostomy: chest

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

The algorithm target is the hands of the operating medical professionals.

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Accuracy

DATA SETS

Data source(s)

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

The procedure videos are captured from egocentric view with by head-mounting the camera, GoPro 7 (minimum). The device is capable of capturing videos in MP4 format with high frame rates and resolution, ensuring accurate visual representation of the medical procedures. We have collected various procedures under different environments to increase the diversity of our dataset.

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

We used human-in-the-loop (HITL) and bootstrapping method for the data annotation of hand tracking. The preprocessing of annotation data, including hand detection, bounding box coordinates, and bounding box areas, are generated using Mediapipe hand detection model. The annotated data is further determined as either left or right based on some preset rules. The algorithm outputs will then be used as the preliminary data file and undergo human inspections. We manually corrected misclassified hands and misplaced bounding boxes.

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

The procedure videos were collected by trained military medics and medical professionals with extensive experience in performing the documented procedures, including the representatives from Purdue University, The Geneva Foundation, Madigan Army Medical center, the Ready Medic One Research Team, and the University of Calgary.

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

All of the physicians have over 10 years of clinical experience. They mounted the GoPro camera on their heads and adjusted the camera angle for the video collection. Ideally, the hands were in the center of the image during the procedure.

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

Each case involves tracking hand movements and identifying the hand type. It should include the exact bounding box coordinates (min_x, max_x, min_y, max_y), along with the corresponding width and height. Additionally, the hand type must be correctly recognized as either the left hand or the right hand.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

Currently, the dataset for training contains 30 videos with 65,127 frames. Each frame includes i) the x coordinate and y coordinate for the bounding box ii) the image width and height iii) the hand category iv) bounding box area v) frame number. We are creating more annotations for the challenge. When the challenge starts, the estimated number for training set will be 40 videos with about 104,392 cases (80%) and the testing set will be 10 videos with 26,098 cases (20%).

c) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

The total number of cases is based on availability of videos. The dataset is split based on a common practice in machine learning research, 80% for training and 20% for testing. The training set can be further split into training and validation set based on the needs of the participants.

d) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

N/A

e) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

This task is new to the Trauma THOMPSON Challenge and all data are unpublished.

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

The annotations for hand tracking follow the COCO format, where each detected hand is represented as an annotated object with specific attributes. The expected test output includes precise bounding box coordinates (x, y, width, height) that define the region containing the hand. Each hand instance is assigned a category label indicating whether it is a left or right hand. 2 human annotators were involved in creating and reviewing the annotations.

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

The hand tracking annotation involves a combination of automated detection and manual refinement. Initially, hand regions are detected using the Mediapipe hand detection model, which generates bounding box coordinates and identifies hand positions. The detected hands are then classified as left or right based on predefined rules. These preliminary annotations serve as a starting point and undergo human inspection to ensure accuracy. Any misclassified hands or incorrectly placed bounding boxes are manually corrected.

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

The hand tracking annotations were initially generated using the Mediapipe hand detection model, which provided bounding box coordinates and classified hands as left or right based on predefined rules. These preliminary annotations were then reviewed and manually corrected by college students to ensure accuracy. The review process involved verifying hand classifications and adjusting bounding boxes for any misclassified or misplaced annotations, resulting in high-quality labeled data for hand tracking.

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

We have the specific annotation for each image and don't need to deal with multiple annotations for one case.

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

To standardize the dataset, bounding box coordinates are normalized, and irrelevant frames with no hand presence are filtered out.

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter-and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

The bounding box positions in the training and testing sets may occasionally be inaccurate because the human annotators miss the misalignment. However, such errors will likely be corrected and not be carried over to subsequent frames.

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

N/A

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

The evaluation of hand tracking is conducted through Multiple Object Tracking Precision (MOTP) metric.

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

MOTP measures the accuracy of predicted hand positions relative to ground truth annotations. It quantifies the average localization error by calculating the Intersection over Union (IoU) between detected and actual hand bounding boxes. A higher MOTP score indicates more precise tracking with minimal deviation.

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking.

We will rank the performance of hand tracking using MOTP scores, which range from 0 to 1. A score of 1 indicates a perfect overlap with the ground truth data, representing high tracking accuracy. Conversely, a score of 0 signifies no overlap, reflecting poor performance.

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

If the algorithm submitted by participants misses an action or an answer, it will be treated as an incorrect result and receive an accuracy of 0 in task evaluation. Therefore, missing results will negatively impact model performance, so we do not recommend that algorithms produce incomplete test results.

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

MOTP directly measures the accuracy of detected hand positions relative to ground truth annotations. Since hand tracking requires accurate spatial localization, ranking based on MOTP prioritizes models that can generate precise bounding boxes with minimal deviation. This method ensures that the best-performing models are those

that consistently detect hands with high spatial accuracy.

Statistical analyses

a) Provide details for the statistical methods used in the scope of the challenge analysis. This may include

- description of the missing data handling,
- details about the assessment of variability of rankings,
- description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions, required for the particular statistical approach, or
- indication of any software product that was used for all data analysis methods.

Due to poor visualization of some actions, the corresponding annotations cannot be correctly generated and thus are deleted from the dataset. The cleaned-up annotations are distributed to the participants.

b) Justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used.

This is the most common method of dealing with missing data [4].

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

We intend to evaluate the performance of the algorithms using ensemble methods, including a linear combination, majority voting, and consensus, to determine whether these techniques could identify a potential winner. However, this analysis will be conducted solely for informational purposes and may serve as a baseline for future iterations of the challenge.

TASK 3: Emergency procedure tool detection

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Emergency procedure tool detection is a fundamental yet critically important task in the Trauma Thompson Challenge. This type of algorithm is designed to detect crucial medical instruments throughout the entire emergency response process. Assisted by hand tracking, the algorithm aids healthcare providers in swiftly identifying every medical device involved in an emergency scenario, thereby enabling precise emergency support measures. Therefore, accurate identification of each emergency tool is of utmost importance. Operating under various unpredictable medical conditions, recognizing medical instruments that may differ in color, shape, but share the same function remains highly challenging. An accurate and broadly applicable emergency tool detection algorithm serves as the cornerstone for implementing emergency procedures, ensuring that the patient's emergency care process is conducted rapidly, correctly, and effectively.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

Emergency procedure, Tool detection

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

Yupeng Zhuo, Juan Wachs, Xiangchen Yu, Aditya Pachpande, Andrew W. Kirkpatrick, Jessica Mckee, Edgar Rojas-Muñoz, Brian Vanvoorst, Jin Tae Kwak, Stas Tiomkin

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

Yupeng Zhuo, Juan Wachs

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

MICCAI

b) Report the platform (e.g. grand-challenge.org) used to run the challenge.

grand-challenge.org

c) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

<https://thompson-challenge.grand-challenge.org> This is the grand-challenge website.

<https://coolstudy.ca/miccai-challenge/> This is the website to download the dataset.

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed (e.g. only (semi-) automatic methods allowed).

Fully automatic

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or to publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets.

No additional data allowed

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

May participate but not eligible for awards and not listed in leaderboard

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

1st place: \$300

2nd place: \$150

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly. Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

Submission of a paper (min 6 pages, max 12 pages) is not required for participating in the challenge and appearing on the leaderboard, but it is required for eligibility of awards.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

Algorithms will be assessed automatically online. To submit results, the participants need to containerize their codes with Docker and upload them to the Trauma THOMPSON grand-challenge website, as described by the submission instructions of the grand-challenge website (<https://grand-challenge.org/documentation/prepare-your-code-for-containerization/>). The submitted containers will be automatically evaluated, and the results and rankings will be visible on the grand-challenge website after a few minutes. Participants can request withdrawals at any time. Sample Docker container codes for all tasks will be provided by the organizing team.

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

Participants of all tasks are permitted to make multiple submissions, with only the last run being officially considered as the final result. However, all participants are restricted to a maximum of 10 submissions per task over the entire challenge period, excluding failed attempts due to incorrect formatting. The restrictions on the number of allowed submissions will prevent leaderboard engineering, ensuring a fair evaluation by discouraging excessive trial-and-error tuning and promoting generalizable model performance. The same submission policy is applied to both individual and group participants.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
- the registration date/period
- the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
- the submission date(s)
- associated workshop days (if any)
- the release date(s) of the results

Challenge website: Apr. 1st, 2025

Participants will be able to register for the challenge on the grand-challenge website.

Train and test data release: Apr. 15th, 2025

Both train and test data will be released.

Containerized algorithm submission deadline: Aug. 15th, 2025

All participants must submit their containerized algorithms by this date to participate in the challenge and appear

on the leaderboard.

Summary report submission: Sep. 1st, 2025

All participants must submit their report papers by this date to be eligible for awards.

Invitation to participate: Sep. 1st, 2025

Winners of the challenge (with both contain and paper submission) will be invited to present at the conference.

The presentation types will be determined by the availability of the participants.

Winner announcement: Sept. 23-27, 2025 (Challenge at MICCAI)

Top 3 performing teams and winners will be announced during the satellite event at the MICCAI conference.

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

Ethics approval is not necessary for the data.

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

The organizing team will provide sample Docker containers to help all participants to package their codes for automatic evaluations on the grand-challenge website, allowing the participants to adhere to the specified input and output formats. The organizing team will use grand-challenge API and the rankings will be automatically produced. The instructions and details are available on the grand-challenge website documentation (<https://grand-challenge.org/documentation/automated-evaluation/>). Additionally, the organizing team will provide codes of some baseline models for each task and the codes for evaluation. Since the challenge has not started, the codes for proposal review can be accessed through this link

(<https://github.com/zhuoyp/TraumaTHOMPSON/blob/main/README.md>).

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

The code from participating teams will remain private. However, the methodologies of the top 3 algorithms will be shared upon announcing the winners. Participants are also free to publish their methodologies once the dataset is made publicly available.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

The organizers will not participate in the challenge, so no participants will have access to the dataset beforehand to ensure fairness.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

Decision support, Assistance

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization

- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Detection,Localization

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

The final biomedical application is for physicians and untrained personnel to perform diagnoses or life-saving resuscitative procedures in resource-limited environments.

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

The challenge dataset is acquired from military medics and medical experts as they perform specific procedures on various medical simulators.

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

All images are extracted from egocentric videos recorded using head-mounted cameras, such as the GoPro 7.

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

The dataset encompasses annotation files in YOLO format, extracted frames, and videos.

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

Manikins are used, and no human subjects are involved.

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary,

differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

- Interosseous insertion: shoulder, limb
- Needle thoracostomy: chest
- Tourniquet application: limb
- Tracheostomy: larynx
- Tube thoracostomy: chest

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

The algorithm target is the tools used in the emergency care procedures, including tourniquet, windlass, label, pen, needle, needle container, and catheter.

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Accuracy

DATA SETS

Data source(s)

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

The procedure videos are captured from egocentric view with by head-mounting the camera, GoPro 7 (minimum). The device is capable of capturing videos in MP4 format with high frame rates and resolution, ensuring accurate visual representation of the medical procedures. We have collected various procedures under different environments to increase the diversity of our dataset.

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

For tool detection annotations, we employed a human-in-the-loop (HITL) and bootstrapping approach similar to the hand-tracking process. The preprocessing of annotation data, including tool detection, bounding box coordinates, and bounding box areas, was performed using pretrained YOLO v7 models. The algorithm-generated outputs served as preliminary annotation files and were then reviewed through human inspection. Any misclassified tools or inaccurately placed bounding boxes were manually corrected to refine the dataset and improve annotation accuracy.

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

The procedure videos were collected by trained military medics and medical professionals with extensive experience in performing the documented procedures, including the representatives from Purdue University, The Geneva Foundation, Madigan Army Medical center, the Ready Medic One Research Team, and the University of Calgary.

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

All of the physicians have over 10 years of clinical experience. They mounted the GoPro camera on their heads and adjusted the camera angle for the video collection. Ideally, the hands were in the center of the image during the procedure.

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

One case is a single frame with annotated bounding boxes of medical tools. Each case represents a unique instance of tool detection and classification.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

The dataset contains approximately 24,000 cases for training and 6,000 cases for testing, thus about 30,000 cases in total.

c) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

The total number of cases is based on availability of videos. The dataset is split based on a common practice in machine learning research, 80% for training and 20% for testing. The training set can be further split into training and validation set based on the needs of the participants.

d) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

N/A

e) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

This task is new to the Trauma THOMPSON Challenge and all data are unpublished.

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

The annotations for object detection follow the YOLO format, where each detected object is represented by a set of numerical values. The expected test output includes the class label, followed by the normalized bounding box coordinates: center_x, center_y, width, and height, all scaled between 0 and 1 relative to the image dimensions. Each detected object is assigned a specific category corresponding to the tool type. 3 human annotators were involved in creating and reviewing the annotations.

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

The tool detection annotation also combines automated detection with human validation to ensure accuracy. Initially, pretrained YOLO object detection models are used to identify tools and generate bounding box coordinates. Each detected tool has a category label. The preliminary annotations are then reviewed through human inspection to correct any misidentified tools or misplaced bounding boxes.

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

The tool detection annotations were generated using pretrained YOLO v7 models, which provided initial bounding box coordinates and assigned category labels to the detected tools. These automated annotations served as a preliminary dataset and were subsequently reviewed and manually corrected by college students. The students carefully examined each annotation by drawing the bounding boxes and tool types on the images.

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

We have the specific annotation for each image and don't need to deal with multiple annotations for one case.

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

To ensure consistency, the bounding box coordinates are normalized, and frames without relevant tool presence are filtered out.

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter-and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

Missed annotations can occur when tools are partially obscured or positioned in cluttered settings, making them difficult to detect accurately.

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

N/A

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

We report Mean Average Precision (mAP) for the evaluation of the tool detection task.

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

mAP is a standard object detection metrics and using it ensures accuracy and reliability. It measures the precision-recall performance across different Intersection over Union (IoU) thresholds. IoU quantifies the overlap between predicted and ground truth bounding boxes.

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking.

We will rank the algorithms based on their mAP, with higher values indicating better performance. In the event of ties, secondary criteria such as computational efficiency or speed may be considered to break the tie.

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

If the algorithm submitted by participants misses an action or an answer, it will be treated as an incorrect result and receive an accuracy of 0 in task evaluation. Therefore, missing results will negatively impact model performance, so we do not recommend that algorithms produce incomplete test results.

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

mAP is ideal because it provides a comprehensive evaluation of a model's detection performance across different confidence levels and Intersection over Union (IoU) thresholds. mAP considers both precision and recall.

Statistical analyses

a) Provide details for the statistical methods used in the scope of the challenge analysis. This may include

- description of the missing data handling,
- details about the assessment of variability of rankings,
- description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions, required for the particular statistical approach, or

- indication of any software product that was used for all data analysis methods.

Due to poor visualization of some actions, the corresponding annotations cannot be correctly generated and thus are deleted from the dataset. The cleaned-up annotations are distributed to the participants.

b) Justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used.

This is the most common method of dealing with missing data [4].

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

We intend to evaluate the performance of the algorithms using ensemble methods, including a linear combination, majority voting, and consensus, to determine whether these techniques could identify a potential winner. However, this analysis will be conducted solely for informational purposes and may serve as a baseline for future iterations of the challenge.

TASK 4: Realism assessment

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

The realism assessment task requires participants to identify how realistic a simulated trauma procedure video appears from an egocentric point of view. Algorithms must be able to identify the realism of a video segment, using information about the procedure including steps, tools, and other important aspects of surgery. This would allow for the curation of higher quality training datasets, which would allow algorithms to learn the most accurate and realistic surgical processes, an essential step of improving accuracy in trauma care delivery assistance.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

Simulation, Simulator evaluation

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

Yupeng Zhuo, Juan Wachs, Eddie Zhang, Andrew W. Kirkpatrick, Jessica Mckee, Edgar Rojas-Muñoz, Brian Vanvoorst, Jin Tae Kwak, Stas Tiomkin

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

Yupeng Zhuo, Juan Wachs

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

MICCAI

b) Report the platform (e.g. grand-challenge.org) used to run the challenge.

grand-challenge.org

c) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

<https://thompson-challenge.grand-challenge.org> This is the grand-challenge website.

<https://coolstudy.ca/miccai-challenge/> This is the website to download the dataset.

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed (e.g. only (semi-) automatic methods allowed).

Fully automatic

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or to publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets.

No additional data allowed

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

May participate but not eligible for awards and not listed in leaderboard

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

1st place: \$300

2nd place: \$150

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly. Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

Submission of a paper (min 6 pages, max 12 pages) is not required for participating in the challenge and appearing on the leaderboard, but it is required for eligibility of awards.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

Algorithms will be assessed automatically online. To submit results, the participants need to containerize their codes with Docker and upload them to the Trauma THOMPSON grand-challenge website, as described by the submission instructions of the grand-challenge website

(<https://grand-challenge.org/documentation/prepare-your-code-for-containerization/>). The submitted containers will be automatically evaluated, and the results and rankings will be visible on the grand-challenge website after a few minutes. Participants can request withdrawals at any time. Sample Docker container codes for all tasks will be provided by the organizing team.

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

Participants of all tasks are permitted to make multiple submissions, with only the last run being officially considered as the final result. However, all participants are restricted to a maximum of 10 submissions per task over the entire challenge period, excluding failed attempts due to incorrect formatting. The restrictions on the number of allowed submissions will prevent leaderboard engineering, ensuring a fair evaluation by discouraging excessive trial-and-error tuning and promoting generalizable model performance. The same submission policy is applied to both individual and group participants.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
- the registration date/period
- the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
- the submission date(s)
- associated workshop days (if any)
- the release date(s) of the results

Challenge website: Apr. 1st, 2025

Participants will be able to register for the challenge on the grand-challenge website.

Train and test data release: Apr. 15th, 2025

Both train and test data will be released.

Containerized algorithm submission deadline: Aug. 15th, 2025

All participants must submit their containerized algorithms by this date to participate in the challenge and appear on the leaderboard.

Summary report submission: Sep. 1st, 2025

All participants must submit their report papers by this date to be eligible for awards.

Invitation to participate: Sep. 1st, 2025

Winners of the challenge (with both contain and paper submission) will be invited to present at the conference. The presentation types will be determined by the availability of the participants.

Winner announcement: Sept. 23-27, 2025 (Challenge at MICCAI)

Top 3 performing teams and winners will be announced during the satellite event at the MICCAI conference.

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

Ethics approval is not necessary for the data.

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

The organizing team will provide sample Docker containers to help all participants to package their codes for automatic evaluations on the grand-challenge website, allowing the participants to adhere to the specified input and output formats. The organizing team will use grand-challenge API and the rankings will be automatically produced. The instructions and details are available on the grand-challenge website documentation (<https://grand-challenge.org/documentation/automated-evaluation/>). Additionally, the organizing team will provide codes of some baseline models for each task and the codes for evaluation. Since the challenge has not started, the codes for proposal review can be accessed through this link (<https://github.com/zhuoyop/TraumaTHOMPSON/blob/main/README.md>).

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

The code from participating teams will remain private. However, the methodologies of the top 3 algorithms will be shared upon announcing the winners. Participants are also free to publish their methodologies once the dataset is made publicly available.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

The organizers will not participate in the challenge, so no participants will have access to the dataset beforehand to ensure fairness.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

Decision support, Assistance

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling

- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Classification

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

The final biomedical application is for physicians and untrained personnel to perform diagnoses or life-saving resuscitative procedures in resource-limited environments.

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

The challenge dataset is acquired from military medics and medical experts as they perform specific procedures on various medical simulators.

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

All images are extracted from egocentric videos recorded using head-mounted cameras, such as the GoPro 7.

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

The dataset encompasses videos with camera information and annotations of realism scores (out of 10) .

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

Manikins are used, and no human subjects are involved.

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

- Interosseous insertion: shoulder, limb
- Needle thoracostomy: chest
- Tourniquet application: limb
- Tracheostomy: larynx
- Tube thoracostomy: chest

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

The algorithm target is identifying key factors, such as the presence of blood, which help verify the realism of a regular or just-in-time lifesaving procedure.

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Accuracy

DATA SETS

Data source(s)

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

The procedure videos are captured from egocentric view with by head-mounting the camera, GoPro 7 (minimum). The device is capable of capturing videos in MP4 format with high frame rates and resolution, ensuring accurate visual representation of the medical procedures. We have collected various procedures under different environments to increase the diversity of our dataset.

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

The medical professionals followed the video collection guidelines adapted from the EPIC Kitchen challenge [2]. The cameras were head mounted to obtain egocentric views of medical procedures. The videos were recorded in controlled environments simulating field conditions, focusing on procedures performed by military medics and medical experts. Each video captured the use of medical tools in real-time scenarios. Protocols for imaging included optimal lighting setups, ensuring minimal shadows and clear visibility of tools, and maintaining consistent camera angles to standardize dataset quality. The obtained videos were stored as MP4 files. They were annotated by timestamps and also extracted into frames. Both the annotated videos and frames are provided for the challenge.

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

The procedure videos were collected by trained military medics and medical professionals with extensive experience in performing the documented procedures, including the representatives from Purdue University, The Geneva Foundation, Madigan Army Medical center, the Ready Medic One Research Team, and the University of Calgary.

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

All of the physicians have over 10 years of clinical experience. They mounted the GoPro camera on their heads and adjusted the camera angle for the video collection. Ideally, the hands were in the center of the image during the procedure.

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

In the realism detection task, each case involves the video of the lifesaving procedure and a corresponding annotation for its realism score in both the training and testing set. For each test case, the algorithms must be able to output a realism score for each video in the test set.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

Currently, the dataset contains 50 videos, with an 80-20 split used for training and testing. For the challenge, we expect to have 175 cases (80%) for the training set, 43 cases (20%) for the testing set, and 218 cases in total.

c) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

The total number of cases is based on availability of videos. The dataset is split based on a common practice in machine learning research, 80% for training and 20% for testing. The training set can be further split into training and validation set based on the needs of the participants.

d) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

N/A

e) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

This task is new to the Trauma THOMPSON Challenge and all data are unpublished.

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

The realism score is determined based on a set of metrics and is evaluated out of 10. The score is assigned based on a list of questions designed to capture key perceptual factors influencing realism. Each question in the evaluation generates a binary answer, and the total score is obtained by summing these binary values. The questions assess various aspects of the patient's condition, including movement, presence of injuries, bodily fluids, anatomical coherence, and overall human-like appearance. The expected test output should be a realism score that is out of 10. 2 human annotators were involved in creating and reviewing the annotations.

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

The realism assessment annotation involves human evaluators who systematically review the emergency procedural videos and assess their resemblance to real-world medical scenarios. Each video is assigned a realism score based on predefined criteria, ensuring consistency in evaluation.

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

The realism assessment annotations were conducted entirely by human evaluators, with college students reviewing the procedural videos. Key factors were assessed to evaluate resemblance to real-world medical scenarios. Each video was assigned a realism score based on predefined evaluation criteria, ensuring consistency and reliability in the assessment.

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

We have the specific annotation for each video and don't need to deal with multiple annotations for one case.

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

This realism score, along with the video ID, will be provided to all percipients in a CSV file.

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter-and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

Since the annotation is produced based on subjective evaluations, inconsistent annotation between different cases may occur.

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

N/A

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

The evaluation of realism assessment is based on accuracy, which measures how well the predicted realism scores align with human-annotated ground truth labels.

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

We choose accuracy as our evaluation metric because it is a very popular and common method for classification tasks. It is calculated as the percentage of correctly classified assessments compared to the total number of evaluations.

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking.

The top 1 accuracy is used for ranking.

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

If the algorithm submitted by participants misses an action or an answer, it will be treated as an incorrect result and receive an accuracy of 0 in task evaluation. Therefore, missing results will negatively impact model performance, so we do not recommend that algorithms produce incomplete test results.

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

The accuracy metric is used for the realism assessment task, as it is a common performance ranking metric in classification tasks.

Statistical analyses

a) Provide details for the statistical methods used in the scope of the challenge analysis. This may include

- description of the missing data handling,

- details about the assessment of variability of rankings,
- description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions, required for the particular statistical approach, or
- indication of any software product that was used for all data analysis methods.

Due to poor visualization of some actions, the corresponding annotations cannot be correctly generated and thus are deleted from the dataset. The cleaned-up annotations are distributed to the participants.

b) Justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used.

This is the most common method of dealing with missing data [4].

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

We intend to evaluate the performance of the algorithms using ensemble methods, including a linear combination, majority voting, and consensus, to determine whether these techniques could identify a potential winner. However, this analysis will be conducted solely for informational purposes and may serve as a baseline for future iterations of the challenge.

TASK 5: Visual Question Answering

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

The visual question answering (VQA) task requires participants to answer various questions about egocentric images from surgical procedures. They must be able to identify the correct answers to any given question relating to tools, next steps, and other components of surgery. Although multiple VQA datasets exist (VQAv2, Coco, etc.), the Trauma THOMPSON VQA dataset is unique as it is the first to utilize egocentric trauma surgery data when prompting the participant for an answer. The algorithms implemented by participants must be innovative enough to analyze complex trauma surgery images and be able to generate an answer to any question related to that image. This aids in more accurate decision-making and less confusion among healthcare providers performing trauma care procedures.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

Multimodal, Vision language model, Visual question answering

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

Yupeng Zhuo, Juan Wachs, Eddie Zhang, Andrew W. Kirkpatrick, Jessica Mckee, Edgar Rojas-Muñoz, Brian Vanvoorst, Jin Tae Kwak, Stas Tiomkin

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

Yupeng Zhuo, Juan Wachs

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

MICCAI

b) Report the platform (e.g. grand-challenge.org) used to run the challenge.

grand-challenge.org

c) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

<https://thompson-challenge.grand-challenge.org> This is the grand-challenge website.

<https://coolstudy.ca/miccai-challenge/> This is the website to download the dataset.

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed (e.g. only (semi-) automatic methods allowed).

Fully automatic

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or to publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets.

No additional data allowed

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

May participate but not eligible for awards and not listed in leaderboard

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

1st place: \$300

2nd place: \$150

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly. Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

Submission of a paper (min 6 pages, max 12 pages) is not required for participating in the challenge and appearing on the leaderboard, but it is required for eligibility of awards.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

Algorithms will be assessed automatically online. To submit results, the participants need to containerize their codes with Docker and upload them to the Trauma THOMPSON grand-challenge website, as described by the submission instructions of the grand-challenge website (<https://grand-challenge.org/documentation/prepare-your-code-for-containerization/>). The submitted containers will be automatically evaluated, and the results and rankings will be visible on the grand-challenge website after a few minutes. Participants can request withdrawals at any time. Sample Docker container codes for all tasks will be provided by the organizing team.

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

Participants of all tasks are permitted to make multiple submissions, with only the last run being officially considered as the final result. However, all participants are restricted to a maximum of 10 submissions per task over the entire challenge period, excluding failed attempts due to incorrect formatting. The restrictions on the number of allowed submissions will prevent leaderboard engineering, ensuring a fair evaluation by discouraging excessive trial-and-error tuning and promoting generalizable model performance. The same submission policy is applied to both individual and group participants.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
- the registration date/period
- the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
- the submission date(s)
- associated workshop days (if any)
- the release date(s) of the results

Challenge website: Apr. 1st, 2025

Participants will be able to register for the challenge on the grand-challenge website.

Train and test data release: Apr. 15th, 2025

Both train and test data will be released.

Containerized algorithm submission deadline: Aug. 15th, 2025

All participants must submit their containerized algorithms by this date to participate in the challenge and appear

on the leaderboard.

Summary report submission: Sep. 1st, 2025

All participants must submit their report papers by this date to be eligible for awards.

Invitation to participate: Sep. 1st, 2025

Winners of the challenge (with both contain and paper submission) will be invited to present at the conference.

The presentation types will be determined by the availability of the participants.

Winner announcement: Sept. 23-27, 2025 (Challenge at MICCAI)

Top 3 performing teams and winners will be announced during the satellite event at the MICCAI conference.

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

Ethics approval is not necessary for the data.

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

The organizing team will provide sample Docker containers to help all participants to package their codes for automatic evaluations on the grand-challenge website, allowing the participants to adhere to the specified input and output formats. The organizing team will use grand-challenge API and the rankings will be automatically produced. The instructions and details are available on the grand-challenge website documentation (<https://grand-challenge.org/documentation/automated-evaluation/>). Additionally, the organizing team will provide codes of some baseline models for each task and the codes for evaluation. Since the challenge has not started, the codes for proposal review can be accessed through this link

(<https://github.com/zhuoyp/TraumaTHOMPSON/blob/main/README.md>).

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

The code from participating teams will remain private. However, the methodologies of the top 3 algorithms will be shared upon announcing the winners. Participants are also free to publish their methodologies once the dataset is made publicly available.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

The organizers will not participate in the challenge, so no participants will have access to the dataset beforehand to ensure fairness.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

Decision support, Assistance

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization

- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Multimodal, Visual Question Answering

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

The final biomedical application is for physicians and untrained personnel to perform diagnoses or life-saving resuscitative procedures in resource-limited environments.

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

The challenge dataset is acquired from military medics and medical experts as they perform specific procedures on various medical simulators.

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

All images are extracted from egocentric videos recorded using head-mounted cameras, such as the GoPro 7.

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

The dataset encompasses annotations of questions, answers, and corresponding extracted frames.

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

Manikins are used, and no human subjects are involved.

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary,

differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

- Interosseous insertion: shoulder, limb
- Needle thoracostomy: chest
- Tourniquet application: limb
- Tracheostomy: larynx
- Tube thoracostomy: chest

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

The algorithm target is the simulated wound area on manikins.

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Accuracy

DATA SETS

Data source(s)

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

The procedure videos are captured from egocentric view with by head-mounting the camera, GoPro 7 (minimum). The device is capable of capturing videos in MP4 format with high frame rates and resolution, ensuring accurate visual representation of the medical procedures. We have collected various procedures under different environments to increase the diversity of our dataset.

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

The annotation for the Visual Question Answering task is entirely human-generated. Experienced annotators manually create question-answer pairs based on the video data. Frames with similar answers were propagated. This approach ensures accuracy and contextual relevance and enhances the dataset's reliability for training and evaluating machine learning models.

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

The procedure videos were collected by trained military medics and medical professionals with extensive experience in performing the documented procedures, including the representatives from Purdue University, The Geneva Foundation, Madigan Army Medical center, the Ready Medic One Research Team, and the University of Calgary.

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

All of the physicians have over 10 years of clinical experience. They mounted the GoPro camera on their heads and adjusted the camera angle for the video collection. Ideally, the hands were in the center of the image during the procedure.

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

Images were extracted from the video clips and annotated with questions and answers. One case includes one image and multiple questions and corresponding answers. It will be available on the download page of our challenge website. Each question is annotated with at least one concise answer. Annotations on the training set will be publicly available. The testing set only has questions of the images.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

The dataset contains approximately 475,000 cases (80%) for training and 119,000 cases for testing, thus about 594,000 cases in total.

c) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

The total number of cases is based on availability of videos. The dataset is split based on a common practice in machine learning research, 80% for training and 20% for testing. The training set can be further split into training and validation set based on the needs of the participants.

d) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

N/A

e) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

New and more challenging questions will be added to the VQA task. 20% of the total data will be new.

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

The dataset annotations include the start and end timestamps, along with the corresponding action for each video clip. The expected test output is action, verb, and noun labels. After recording, physicians will annotate their own procedural videos by providing timestamps, action labels, and question-answer pairs related to the procedure steps in the collected footage. 3 human annotators were involved in creating and reviewing the annotations.

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

The annotations of VQA are entirely human generated to ensure contextual accuracy and relevance. Annotators manually answer questions about frame extracted from the procedural videos, focusing on key actions, medical tools, and decision-making steps. Each question is carefully designed to assess comprehension of the procedure, while the corresponding answers provide precise and informative responses.

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

All of the physicians have over 10 years of experience in the clinical settings.

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

We have the specific annotation for each image and don't need to deal with multiple annotations for one case.

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

Images were extracted directly from the recorded procedures of military medics and medical experts. Key frames with plentiful information were manually picked and then annotated with multiple questions and corresponding answers.

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter-and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

Ambiguity in the phrasing of questions or answers may lead to misinterpretations, resulting in inconsistent annotations.

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

N/A

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

We use average accuracy and BLEU score for the evaluation of the VQA task.

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

We evaluate the accuracy, which is the number of exact matches divided by the total test cases, as it is the most common metric. We also use BLEU to evaluate the test results because it is the most common evaluation method that is used to measure the word overlap similarity between the ground truth and the algorithm output answer.

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking.

We take the average accuracy and BLEU score as the algorithm performance to determine the winner. The VQA challenge ranks the participants based on the accuracy first and if the accuracies are same between different teams, we will compare the BLEU scores.

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

If the algorithm submitted by participants misses an action or an answer, it will be treated as an incorrect result and receive an accuracy of 0 in task evaluation. Therefore, missing results will negatively impact model performance, so we do not recommend that algorithms produce incomplete test results.

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

We rank the participants based on the average accuracy first and if it is the same, we use BLEU score, because it is a common practice in semantic tasks.

Statistical analyses

a) Provide details for the statistical methods used in the scope of the challenge analysis. This may include

- description of the missing data handling,
- details about the assessment of variability of rankings,

- description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions, required for the particular statistical approach, or
- indication of any software product that was used for all data analysis methods.

Due to poor visualization of some actions, the corresponding annotations cannot be correctly generated and thus are deleted from the dataset. The cleaned-up annotations are distributed to the participants.

b) Justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used.

This is the most common method of dealing with missing data [4].

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

We intend to evaluate the performance of the algorithms using ensemble methods, including a linear combination, majority voting, and consensus, to determine whether these techniques could identify a potential winner. However, this analysis will be conducted solely for informational purposes and may serve as a baseline for future iterations of the challenge.

ADDITIONAL POINTS

References

Please include any reference important for the challenge design, for example publications on the data, the annotation process or the chosen metrics as well as DOIs referring to data or code.

- [1] A. W. Kirkpatrick, J. L. McKee, P. B. McBeth, C. G. Ball, A. LaPorta, T. Broderick, T. Leslie, D. King, H. E. Wright Beatty, J. Keillor, and H. Tien, "The Damage Control Surgery in Austere Environments Research Group (DCSAERG): A dynamic program to facilitate real-time telerobotics/telediagnosis to address exsanguination in extreme and austere environments," *Journal of Trauma and Acute Care Surgery*, vol. 83, no. 1, 2017.
- [2] D. Damen, H. Doughty, G. M. Farinella, S. Fidler, A. Furnari, E. Kazakos, D. Moltisanti, J. Munro, T. Perrett, W. Price, and M. Wray, "Scaling egocentric vision: The 'Equation Missing' dataset," *Computer Vision – ECCV 2018*, pp. 753–771, 2018.
- [3] Zhao, H., Yan, Z., Wang, H., Torresani, L., Torralba, A.: SLAC: A Sparsely Labeled Dataset for Action Classification and Localization. arXiv preprint arXiv:1712.09374 (2017).
- [4] N. B. Ipsen, P.-A. Mattei, and J. Frellsen, "How to deal with missing data in supervised deep learning?," *ICLR 2022, 10th International Conference on Learning Representations*, Apr-2022.

Further comments

Further comments from the organizers.

N/A